

Thank you for attending the 2024 Environmental Water Manager Workshop. Please refer to this resource for the most updated information on venue, logistics, and agenda.

Environmental Water Manager Workshop

Date & Time	July 18, 2024 9:30 a.m. - 5:00 p.m.
Location	The Exchange Sacramento 1006 4th Street, Sacramento, CA 95814

Goal and Outcomes

Goal

The aim of this workshop is to understand how decision-making by an Environmental Water Manager (EWM) might be reflected and shift priorities within systems operations modeling for the Sacramento watershed, generate buy-in and enthusiasm for model development, and identify a robust external group of advisors to guide the project. With participant input, the EDF and Cornell team seeks to understand which questions this project should pursue, and what resources exist to answer those questions and inform the modeling, and which questions should be reserved for future research.

Desired Outcomes

- Inform key partners and advisors about the EWM Project and identify challenges and opportunities associated with more storage for the environment and more flexible management of environmental flows.
- Develop a common understanding of the state of the science on management of environmental storage and flows, and related modeling efforts.
- Catalog and discuss key scientific insights and datasets that could and should inform the pilot modeling as it is built out for the Sacramento Valley.
- Refine the questions that an updated modeling capability could help answer or explore.
- Identify a set of questions for this project, and for future research beyond the scope of this project, and whether other modeling tools should be considered and/or incorporated.

Detailed Agenda

Agenda Item	Lead	Time	Description
Welcome	Molly Daniels (Environmental Incentives)	9:00 - 9:30 am	Light breakfast and coffee provided. Participants settle in.
Introductions and Overview	Gopal Penny (EDF) & Molly Daniels (Environmental Incentives)	9:30 - 10:00	Share the purpose of the gathering, the agenda, and brief individual introductions. Provide an overview of the joint EDF/Cornell effort, and establish shared understanding of goals and intended outcomes for Phase 1.

Agenda Item	Lead	Time	Description
Expert Panel	Robyn Grimm (EDF)	10:00 - 11:00	<p>Provide an overview of the opportunities and challenges associated with establishment of an environmental water manager, and facilitate discussions with attendees. Panelists include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rene Henery (Trout Unlimited) • Kristal Davis-Fadtke (CA Dept. of Fish & Wildlife) • Kevin Thielen (US Bureau of Reclamation) • Jay Zeigler (CA State Water Resources Control Board) • Jeff Mount (PPIC)
Open Discussion	Robyn Grimm (EDF) & Molly Daniels (Environmental Incentives)	11:00 - 12:00	Participants engage with panelists to discuss key knowledge gaps, challenges, and opportunities.
Lunch Break		12:00 - 1:00	Lunch provided
Pilot Modeling Overview	Pat Reed, Sai Veena Sunkara and Zach Brodeur (Cornell University)	1:00 - 1:30	Brief overview of the concerns in modeling the benefits and challenges of the Environmental Water Manager concept.
Small Group Discussion #1	Gopal Penny (EDF)	1:30 - 2:45	<p>Participants break into small groups and discuss:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What are the benefits of explicitly allocating storage for environmental flows in the Sacramento system?</i> 2. <i>If you were an environmental water manager, what knowledge/ resources would you use/need?</i> 3. <i>What are the challenges associated with establishing an operationally effective environmental water manager within the Sacramento system?</i>
Stretch Break		2:45 - 3:00	Snacks and refreshments provided
Small Group Discussion #2	Patrick Reed (Cornell University)	3:00 - 4:00	<p>Participants break into small groups and discuss:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>What are the highest priorities and evaluation metrics for modeling the tradeoffs and synergies associated with an EWM?</i> 2. <i>What are key regulatory, operational and natural constraints and uncertainties for a modeling effort to capture?</i> 3. <i>What are important resources (datasets, tools, models, etc.) and candidate collaboration opportunities for modeling the implications of EWM decision frameworks and scenarios?</i>

Agenda Item	Lead	Time	Description
Report Out from Groups	Patrick Reed (Cornell University)	4:00 - 4:30	Report back from breakouts and discuss key takeaways as a large group.
Collaboration Opportunities and Convene	Gopal Penny (EDF)	4:30 - 4:50	Discuss future opportunities for collaboration.
Convene and Next Steps	Molly Daniels (Environmental Incentives)	4:50 - 5:00	Summarize key takeaways from the day and provide the next steps of the project.
Optional Happy Hour		5:00 - 7:00	Participants gather nearby for informal drinks and camaraderie.

Booking Travel and Accommodations

The closest airport is the Sacramento International Airport (SMF).

The conference is located at a hotel, the Exchange Sacramento, for convenience. To book a room at the Exchange Sacramento, contact Malik Washington (malik.washington@hilton.com) for a 10% discount by mentioning that you are attending the EWM workshop.

If you prefer to stay elsewhere or the Exchange Sacramento books up, other hotel options in the area can be provided upon request. Please email mdaniels@enviroincentives.com and cprice@enviroincentives.com for suggested hotels.